

Biocatalyst Interactions with Gases (BIG)

Technology Transfer Virtual Event (TTVE)

5 March 2026

Summary

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Section 1: Event Details, Highlights and Agenda

When: 9:00 am - 12:00 pm EST Thursday March 5, 2026

Where: Virtually over Zoom

- Registration via EventBrite
- Advertising for event via EventBrite, LinkedIn, BIG Collaboration page, word of mouth
- WolfBytes assisted with third party hosting duties and technical support
- Live meeting was not recorded
- Documents associated with the event are posted on Zenodo (see Section 5 for URL)

Purpose: The purpose of the event is to broaden the impact of our work by sharing findings and promoting networking with and beyond the Biocatalyst Interactions with Gases (BIG) team. We want to continue promoting the good “vibe” that came with our 2025 BIG Research Symposium.

Acknowledgement: This event was supported by the Novo Nordisk Foundation (Grant no. NNF22SA0078767).

Highlights & Take-Aways

This three-hour virtual webinar-style event featured eight expert speakers involved in projects and initiatives that use enzymes, namely carbonic anhydrase (CA) and formate dehydrogenase (FDH), to accelerate the conversion of carbon dioxide (CO₂) to bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻) or formate, with potential for subsequent bioconversions to commodity chemicals like acetate. The scope of talks spanned from the fundamental science of enzyme design, expression and immobilization to results of lab scale application testing, plans for pilot-scale testing, and projections for technoeconomic feasibility. The webinar attracted 69 participants from 10 countries.

Examples of immediate impact are: increased awareness of progress in the field, reconnections and new connections by researchers in the field, sharing of links to relevant publications during the Q&A, and invitations among participants to contribute to future events being planned by diverse groups.

Key take-aways are:

- With enthusiasm building for research and development on biocatalyzed gas reactions across disciplines, networking events like this are important to build the community.
- Expertise and collaboration across different disciplines is needed to address the special challenges and opportunities of biocatalysts in gas management.
- This condensed virtual event highlighted important ongoing work in the field. The speakers are leading-edge experts - reach out to them to learn more.
- Carbonic anhydrase shows increasing viability as a carbon capture catalyst.
- Formate dehydrogenase (FDH) is under focused study by several research groups, with initial uncertainties overcome for producing and testing FDH enzyme for CO₂ conversion at lab scale, and with some researchers exploring scale-up.
- Eventbrite and Zenodo are useful to manage registration and archive event documents.
- Even short virtual events require ample planning to attract a broad audience - for similar events, seek support from available communications and marketing professionals.

Agenda

Welcome & Introduction	
9:00	Sonja Salmon NCSU Goals and Progress in the Biocatalyst Interactions with Gases (BIG) Collaboration
Session 1: Exploring	
9:15	Jialong Shen NCSU Scalable and Robust Immobilized Carbonic Anhydrase for CO ₂ Reactive Absorption
9:30	Zsófia Bognár DTU High Resolution Imaging of Immobilized Enzyme Systems
9:45	Joe Sagues NCSU Carbonic Anhydrase and the Path to Cost-effective MDEA CO ₂ Capture
10:00	Roman Brunecky NLR Controlled Electrochemical Wiring of FDH via Nanowires and Self-Assembled Interfaces
10:15	Session 1: Panel Q&A Discussion Moderated by Ranjitha Ramakrishnan and Sophie Kargo Kaptain
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Session 2: Advancing	
10:50	Yong Hwan Kim UNIST Defining the Molecular Logic of MeFDH1: Tungsten-Pterin Cofactor Assembly and the Structural Basis of Viologen-Mediated Electron Transfer for CO ₂ Reduction in Large Scale
11:05	Sara Barricella Novonosis Novonosis Big Impact for CO ₂ Valorization
11:20	Lasse Rosendahl CORC CORC - Novo Nordisk Foundation CO ₂ Research Center: research focus and structure
11:35	Session 2: Panel Q&A Discussion Moderated by Cam Hunter and Young Hwang
11:50	Wrap-up & Adjourn Sonja Salmon

Section 2: Speaker Abstracts and Bios

Introduction

9:00 am - Sonja Salmon (NCSU)

Title: Goals and Progress in the Biocatalyst Interactions with Gases (BIG) Collaboration

Abstract: The Biocatalyst Interactions with Gases (BIG) Collaboration between North Carolina State University (NCSU) and the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) is investigating fundamental gas-enzyme-interface interactions for three life-essential gas conversion reactions: 1) conversion of CO₂ to bicarbonate catalyzed by carbonic anhydrase for carbon capture, 2) reduction of CO₂ to formate catalyzed by formate dehydrogenase (FDH) for carbon utilization, and 3) reduction of N₂ to ammonia catalyzed by nitrogenase, the central reaction in nitrogen fixation. Our goals are to build basic knowledge and technology platforms for gas phase enzyme reactions and to explore the feasibility of enzyme-based processes for gas molecule transformations. Addressing these challenges requires expertise, collaboration and knowledge sharing across many disciplines. We are hosting this Technology Translation Virtual Event to share findings from our team as well as highlight the efforts of distinguished researchers in this field, with the goal of inspiring increased curiosity, networking and support that will advance these technologies. We envision that enhancing biocatalyst interactions with gases by minimizing reaction barriers near immobilized enzyme interfaces will ultimately lead to replacements of critical chemical processes with enzymatic approaches that contribute to global sustainability solutions.

Bio: Dr. Sonja Salmon is a professor in the Wilson College of Textiles at North Carolina State University, where she leads the Textile Biocatalysis Research team in the Department of Textile Engineering, Chemistry and Science. After completing a B.S. degree in Textile Chemistry and Ph.D. in Fiber and Polymer Science from NC State, she worked for 22 years at Novozymes North America, Inc., in research and development roles from Scientist to Senior Innovation Manager, developing new enzyme applications for industrial processes including textiles, household care, pulp and paper, waste treatment, biofuels, specialty applications, and CO₂ capture. Central to her current research and teaching is building insights into the diverse interactions possible between enzymes, polymers and fibers, especially biobased materials, and how these can play important roles in making products and processes more sustainable. She leads the Novo Nordisk Foundation funded Biocatalyst Interactions with Gases (BIG) Collaboration that aims to advance enzyme technology for CO₂ capture, CO₂ conversion and N₂ reduction to ammonia, which are critically important in addressing global challenges.

Session 1: Exploring

9:15 am - Jialong Shen (NCSU)

Title: Scalable and Robust Immobilized Carbonic Anhydrase for CO₂ Reactive Absorption

Abstract: Carbonic anhydrase (CA) showed promise as a rate enhancement catalyst for low-energy aqueous solvents used in CO₂ reactive absorption process. Attaching enzymes on solid support surfaces and retaining them in the low temperature absorption column enhances performance lifetime and durability of the biocatalysts. Textiles are ideally suited as enzyme immobilization support and gas-liquid (G-L) contactors because they are lightweight, economical, flexible, and durable materials that can be fabricated in many shapes and have high surface areas and abundance of functional groups for chemical modification and enhanced gas liquid contacts. Biocatalytic textile contactors immobilizing CA on textile fiber surfaces will be easy to scale up in large volumes using textile manufacturing machinery and can be used either as “drop-in” for existing CO₂ reactive absorption facilities or in custom fit novel configurations such as when needed for coupling with downstream CO₂ utilization processes. In lab-scale testing, biocatalytic textiles were compatible with multiple different CO₂ absorption solvents and with CO₂ concentrations ranging from atmospheric to point-source emissions. They can be manufactured in a roll-to-roll pad-dry process using conventional textile wet processing facilities and were shown to withstand repeated washing and drying, immersion and shaking in heated solvents, and continuous testing for up to one thousand hours without performance reduction.

Bio: Dr. Jialong Shen is an Assistant Professor in the Department of Textile Engineering, Chemistry and Science at NC State University. He leads the Sustainable Polymer Research Group, which works at the interface of polymer science, textile engineering, and biotechnology to design sustainable, high-performance fiber and polymer materials. He holds a Ph.D. in Fiber and Polymer Science and previously worked on the Textile Biocatalysis Research team led by Prof. Sonja Salmon; together, they have published several research publications and filed patent applications related to the chemistry and design of scalable biocatalytic textiles for CO₂ capture and conversion.

9:30 am - Zsófia Bognár (DTU)

Title: High Resolution Imaging of Immobilized Enzyme Systems

Co-Authors: Zsófia Bognár¹, Sara Talebi Deylamani^{1,2}, Yasmine Gigi Tokman¹, Guisepee Di Palma², Jeannette de Sparra Lundin³, Sune M. Christensen³, Joerg Jinschek^{1,2}, Stig Helveg¹

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Abstract: Immobilized enzyme systems are attracting interest for biocatalytic flow processes.^{1,2} While the catalytic performance are expected to depend on the enzyme distribution, orientation and anchoring on the support material, detailed understanding is often limited reflecting a lack of nanoscale visualization.³ Here, we combine transmission electron microscopy and confocal laser scanning microscopy to investigate enzymes at high spatial and temporal resolution. Specifically, we focus on carbonic anhydrase and lipase, immobilized on different high-surface-area-supports such as metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and carbon nanotubes.⁴ The combined imaging approach uncovers the spatial arrangement, quantifies their coverage on the support surface, and measures local catalytic activity of the immobilized enzymes.

The high spatiotemporal resolution insight establishes unambiguous dispersion-activity relations in heterogeneously loaded enzyme system and demonstrates, in turn, how local confinement collectively shape biocatalytic performance. Thus, the combined imaging approach enables a framework for rationally engineering immobilized enzyme systems with enhanced stability, accessibility, and functional efficiency.

The project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement (Grant no. 101152937), the Novo Nordisk Foundation through the Biocatalyst Interactions with Gases (BIG) Collaboration (Grant no. NNF22SA0078767). DTU VISION was supported by the Danish National Research Foundation (DNRF146).

References:

- ¹ Bolivar, J. M. et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2022**, 51 (15), 6251-6290
- ² Fedai, M. et al., *Trends in Biotechnology*, **2025**, 43 (12), 3041-3055
- ³ Diamanti, E., et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2024**, 63 (20), e202319248
- ⁴ Deylamani S. T., et al. *Nano Lett.* **2025**, 25 (49), 17122-17128

Bio: Dr. Zsófia Bognár earned her degree in chemical engineering from the Budapest University of Technology and Economics, where she also completed her PhD at the Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry. Her doctoral research focused on developing synthetic receptors and labels for chemical sensing. In 2023, she joined the Center for Visualizing Catalytic Processes (VISION) at the Technical University of Denmark as a Postdoctoral Researcher. There, she contributed to the Biocatalyst Interactions with Gases (BIG) Collaboration, pioneering new biology-based methods for carbon dioxide management and sustainable fertilizer production. In 2024, Zsófia was awarded the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (MSCA-PF) for her project titled "Lipase Immobilization for Microscopic Investigation of Enzyme Activity (lipaseTEM)." Her primary research focus is on developing advanced techniques for visualizing catalytic processes using transmission electron microscopy and fluorescence microscopy. Zsófia's work aims to enhance our understanding of enzyme activity at the microscopic level, driving innovations in sustainable biocatalysis.

9:45 am - Joe Sagues (NCSU)

Title: Carbonic Anhydrase and the Path to Cost-effective MDEA CO₂ Capture

Abstract: With the increasing urgency for global decarbonization, carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) remains essential but faces substantial economic challenges. Conventional amine solvent-based capture methods are limited by high energy requirements and heavy capital investment.

Tertiary amines like methyl diethanolamine (MDEA) offer advantages in terms of thermal stability, lower energy regeneration, and reduced degradation; however, their slow CO₂ absorption kinetics hinder these benefits. We examine the transformative potential of applying Carbonic Anhydrase (CA) to address these limitations. As a biocatalyst, CA drastically enhances the kinetics of capture solvents. By accelerating absorption rates, enzyme-assisted CO₂ capture enables the use of energy-efficient solvents, effectively reducing absorber column sizing and lowering the thermal energy required for regeneration.

This study presents a preliminary techno-economic analysis (TEA) of a CA-enhanced MDEA solvent system to quantify the economic benefits of enzyme integration, discussing how these improvements facilitate the transition from bench-scale demonstration to industrial implementation, and illustrating how biological efficiency can drive the cost reductions necessary for widespread commercial adoption.

Bio: Dr. Joe Sagues is the Principal Investigator of the Biocarbon Utilization & Sequestration (BUS) Lab in the Biological & Agricultural Engineering Department at NC State University. He has experience in research, development, and demonstration of innovative bioprocessing technologies at corporations, startup companies, universities, and national labs. The BUS Lab takes an integrated approach to innovate technologies that utilize and sequester biogenic carbon, with a specific interest in waste materials generated along food production supply chains. The aim of his work is to leverage the bioeconomy for carbon drawdown. He is bridging fundamental advances in synthetic biology and chemical catalysis with bioprocess engineering to innovate carbon-negative bioproducts that range from feed, chemicals, fuels, and materials. When developing a new technology, the BUS Lab takes into account the entire technology-to-market pathway, starting with fundamental research and ending with commercialization. Such a comprehensive approach increases the odds of commercial success by eliminating developmental hurdles and pitfalls at an early stage.

10:00 am - Roman Brunecky (NLR)

Title: Controlled Electrochemical Wiring of FDH via Nanowires and Self-Assembled Interfaces

Abstract: This talk examines electrochemical coupling in formate dehydrogenase (FDH)-based bio electrochemical systems with emphasis on engineering electrode interfaces that enable controlled enzyme orientation and wiring. Earlier FDH electrochemistry work has largely relied on nonspecific adsorption or “drop-cast” enzyme layers on electrodes, limiting reproducibility and

obscuring relationships between electrochemical signals and enzymatic function. In contrast, the current effort focuses on nanowire- and self-assembled monolayer (SAM)-based architectures designed to impose defined spatial organization and electron transfer pathways at the enzyme electrode interface.

This presentation summarizes our current project efforts and reports new measurements validate that key electrochemical features persist under controlled wiring conditions and are not artifacts of poorly defined enzyme attachment. These results provide an internally consistent and interpretable electrochemical baseline that has not previously been broadly disseminated.

Collectively, these results demonstrate the value of nanowires and SAMs as tools for disentangling orientation, proximity, and coupling effects in FDH electrochemistry. The emphasis is on mechanistic understanding of enzyme-electrode interfaces and system-level behavior, establishing a foundation for rational design of more robust and scalable FDH-driven bio electrochemical systems.

Bio: Dr. Roman Brunecky is a senior research scientist at NLR, with primary expertise in enzyme structure function relationships and enzyme material interfaces, best known for his work on cellulases and biomass degrading enzymes. His research spans enzyme expression, purification, and mechanistic characterization, with a long-standing focus on how enzyme orientation, confinement, and surface interactions govern activity and stability. More recently, this expertise has been applied to redox enzymes, including formate dehydrogenase (FDH), in the context of hybrid bio electrochemical and electro-to-microbial (E2M) systems. In this role, Dr. Brunecky brings a mechanistic, enzyme-centric perspective to the design of nanowire- and self-assembled monolayer based interfaces that enable controlled enzyme wiring and interpretable electrochemical behavior. His work emphasizes reproducibility and fundamental understanding of enzyme-interface interactions as a foundation for robust integration of biological catalysts with engineered materials.

Session 2: Advancing

10:50 am - Yong Hwan Kim (UNIST)

Title: Defining the Molecular Logic of MeFDH1: Tungsten-Pterin Cofactor Assembly and the Structural Basis of Viologen-Mediated Electron Transfer for CO₂ Reduction in Large Scale

Abstract: Tungsten-dependent formate dehydrogenase 1 from *Methylobacterium extorquens* (MeFDH1) is a premier biocatalyst for reversible CO₂/formate interconversion, but scalable deployment demands control over both metallocofactor maturation and redox wiring to low-potential mediators. This presentation defines the molecular logic that creates the functional form of MeFDH1 from the cell to the reactor. We first delineate a dedicated tungsten-pterin (W-bis-MGD) assembly and delivery pathway, identifying the MoeA1 insertase and MobB scaffold as key determinants that enforce tungsten selectivity over molybdate and remove a major bottleneck in

producing active holoenzyme. We then resolve the structural basis of viologen (ethyl viologen, EV) electron transfer, revealing a dual-interaction strategy: a primary FMN-centered binding mode and an FMN-independent “aromatic cage” (F232/F471/Y329) that positions EV near the proximal B1 Fe–S cluster to sustain CO₂ reduction when flavin occupancy is limiting. Finally, we translate these insights to process engineering, demonstrating MeFDH1 operation in a 10-L pilot reactor fed with live steel-mill off-gases to achieve molar-scale formate production. Together, these results deliver actionable design rules for improving assembly yields, reducing mediator requirements, and de-risking industrial CO₂-to-formate biomanufacturing.

Bio: Dr. Yong Hwan Kim is a professor at the School of Energy and Chemical Engineering at UNIST (Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology) in Korea. He began his academic career at Seoul National University, where he earned his bachelor's, master's, and Ph.D. degrees. After completing his Ph.D. in 1996, Dr. Kim spent four years in industry, working in R&D at the Samsung Advanced Institute of Technology and Samsung Engineering. He then transitioned to the National Lab (Korea Research Institute of Chemical Technology) as a principal scientist, where he focused on bridging biotechnology and chemical technology. Since 2015, his research has centered on fundamental studies of metalloenzymes, including heme peroxidases and enzymes containing nickel or tungsten that are involved in C1 conversion in academy. Dr. Kim also serves as the director of the Engineering Research Centre for Microplastics treatment (ERC) and the Dean of the College of Engineering at UNIST and member of the National Academy of Engineering of Korea.

11:05 am - Sara Barricella (Novonosis)

Title: Novonosis Big Impact for CO₂ Valorization

Abstract: Novonosis enzymatic carbon capture research is strategically positioned to accelerate the commercialization of CO₂ capture and conversion technologies. Through industrial and academic partnerships, we are advancing carbonic anhydrase (CA)-based solutions toward near-term deployment in real-world applications. In this talk, I will focus on the EU-funded ReUSE project where CA immobilization on cotton-based packing is being investigated for integration in a rotating packed-bed reactor for CO₂ capture and subsequent conversion to formate via electrochemical reduction. Additionally, I will touch upon Novonosis contribution to the acetate-to-food consortium, funded by the Novo Nordisk Foundation and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, which aims to convert CO₂ into acetate via electrolysis for sustainable, food-grade protein production—exemplifying the broader commercial and societal potential of enzymatic CO₂ valorization.

Bio: Dr. Sara Barricella is a biocatalysis and enzyme engineering scientist with a background in Industrial Chemistry from the University of Naples Federico II, where she completed both her bachelor's and master's degrees. She later earned a PhD in Chemical and Biological Engineering from Monash University (Melbourne, Australia) under the supervision of Prof. Gil Garnier, Prof. Victoria Haritos and Prof. Benny Freeman (UT Austin), focusing on enzymatic cascade reactions in continuous flow and the design of compartmentalized biocatalytic systems. Her research

experience includes enzyme immobilization, flow chemistry, and membrane–enzyme interfaces. Sara joined Novonosis as a Postdoctoral Research Scientist to contribute to the Horizon-funded ReUSE project on Enzymatic CO₂ Capture in a Rotating Packed Bed and Electrocatalytic CO₂ Reduction to Useful Products. Her work focuses on designing and optimizing enzyme immobilization strategies to enable scalable, energy-efficient CO₂ capture technologies, bridging fundamental enzymology with applied process development.

11:20 am - Lasse Rosendahl (CORC)

Title: CORC - Novo Nordisk Foundation CO₂ Research Center: research focus and structure

Abstract: CORC operates on a grant from the Novo Nordisk Foundation of approx. 100 M USD over the period 2022-2028. It is a mission driven center, with the objective of carrying out research and development within life sciences and chemistry to accelerate climate-change mitigation by CCUS technologies. CORC is a hub-and-satellite organization, with the hub at Aarhus University (DK), and 9 satellites distributed over Germany, USA, Switzerland, Italy and the UK. Approximately 110 researchers are directly associated with CORC research projects.

CORC combines chemistry and life sciences in three major mission streams: Capturing CO₂, Converting CO₂, and integrated solutions. Biocatalysis is a topic in several of these. A mission enabler stream focusing on AI, machine learning, digital twins and systems modelling, supports the more experimental focus of the three mission streams. It is a key priority of CORC to carry out horizontal interdisciplinary research, across the relevant satellites, as well as to vertically integrate research at different TRLs but within the same value chain, in order to accelerate research towards scale.

CORC welcomes collaboration with other stakeholders, industrial as well as academic.

Bio: Professor Lasse Rosendahl has PhD in Mechanical Engineering and a 30+ year career in academia, focusing on sustainable fuels, renewable energy and CCUS. He is a full professor and served for 6 years as Head of Department in the Department of Energy, Aalborg University, Denmark, before joining Aarhus University and CORC as CEO in March 2025. He is a board member of the Independent Research Fund Denmark (appointed by the Minister of Higher Education & Science), board member of the Danish national CCUS partnership Inno-CCUS, Danish advisor to Horizon Europe Cluster 5 – Climate, Energy and Mobility, Danish node lead for ECCSEL ERIC, the European CCUS research infrastructure consortium and member of the Danish Academy of Technical Sciences.

Section 3: Q&A Summary

A moderator-facilitated panel-style Q&A session occurred after each speaker session. Attendees posted questions and comments using the Zoom Q&A dialog box. The questions were answered verbally during the panel discussion, were answered in writing using the Zoom dialog box during the event, or were answered afterwards in writing when this event summary was prepared. Some responses were edited for clarity.

Session 1: Exploring

1.	<p>Initial question to each Session 1 panelist: What is needed to scale up your technology?</p> <p>Jialong: The textile-based gas-liquid contactor technology is ready to scale up. The technology uses commercially available materials.</p> <p>Zsófia: The enzyme@ZIF-L work is currently at laboratory scale, which is an essential stage for gathering detailed information about the interactions between enzymes and the support matrix. This lab-scale research allows us to evaluate the stability of the immobilized enzymes at the nanoscale. A thorough nanoscale understanding of these immobilized systems is unavoidable, as it provides the fundamental insights needed for future scale-up efforts.</p> <p>Joe: The CA-enhanced MDEA CO₂ capture technology is promising for scale-up and would be ready to go, but has been hindered by on/off investments in the technology.</p> <p>Roman: Currently there are limitations with redox enzymes in general; they can be challenging to produce and suitable electrode materials must be investigated to ensure the enzymatic approach is economically attractive.</p>
2.	<p>Zsófia, your presentation was excellent. I was especially fascinated by the TEM images and the EDS analysis. I have a few questions about the EDS analysis and would love to learn more about it. In your slide you mentioned the enzyme size is about 5 nm, and the EDS map shows sulfur inside the ZIF-L. Is this sulfur only coming from the cysteine residues in the enzyme? If yes, how many cysteine residues does one PmCA enzyme have? In the 50 nm EDS map, the sulfur signal looks very strong and spread out. Does this mean many enzymes are inside each cavity, or is it because of the EDS resolution?</p> <p>Zsófia: Thank you! Yes, the only elemental difference between PmCA and ZIF-L is sulfur, which originates exclusively from the enzyme. PmCA contains 2 cysteine residues and 8 methionines, so all detected sulfur in the EDS maps comes from the enzyme itself.</p> <p>Because EDS has a limited spatial resolution, it cannot resolve individual enzymes at the nanoscale. As mentioned in the presentation, the enzyme does not occupy the intrinsic ZIF-L cavities due to the large size mismatch. Instead, during <i>in situ</i> entrapment, new nanometer-sized cavities form around the enzyme, and these are distributed throughout the crystal. Therefore, the sulfur signal appears relatively weak</p>

	<p>but broadly distributed across the ZIF-L particle. This reflects both the concentration level of the enzyme throughout the crystal and the limited resolution of the EDS technique, rather than indicating a high number of enzymes confined within each cavity. With a loading of approximately 250 µg PmCA per mg ZIF-L, the total amount of sulfur present is detectable but not high enough to produce sharp, localized hotspots. All parameters for the measurements and results can be found in our paper: https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.nanolett.5c04684</p>
3.	<p>A participant representing Cascade Bio shared: We're working on enzyme immobilization and biocatalysts using a novel immobilization technology based on polymer brushes. At this time - we're not working on carbon capture, although something we are very excited about. We are mainly serving the fine & specialty chemicals and pharmaceutical markets. Really enjoying the presentations so far!</p>
4.	<p>A postdoc participant from Rutgers University shared: My background is in protein biophysics especially at interfaces. I'm just starting to get into biocatalysis, and I'm enjoying learning about the work you all are doing!</p>
5.	<p>Jesse Thompson from University of Kentucky shared: Please find our newest ASAP paper covering CA-mimic compounds for DAC! The first author PB is now working with Dr. Salmon and Dr. Shen at NC State. https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.5c06296</p> <p>Sonja: Jesse, great to "see" you and of course we are delighted to have PB working with us on the BIG Collaboration! Also, for others in the audience - if you are working in carbon capture and have not connected with Jesse and the folks at University of Kentucky - you should!! Great test facilities!</p>
6.	<p>Zsófia, MOF-based enzyme immobilization looks very promising, but MOFs can be expensive to produce at large scale. Do you think this approach can realistically be scaled up for industrial CO₂ capture?</p> <p>Zsófia: Until recently, one of the biggest barriers to industrial CO₂ capture using MOFs (with or without enzymes) was cost and production volume. However, this situation seems to be changing: BASF now produces MOFs at several hundred tons per year, marking the first true industrial-scale MOF manufacturing capability. This is already being used for CO₂ capture platforms developed by Svante Technologies: https://www.thechemicalengineer.com/news/basf-commercially-produces-metal-organic-frameworks-for-co2-capture-in-world-first/</p> <p>This demonstrates that the material supply chain is successfully scaling, an essential requirement for enzyme@MOF technologies to follow. Enzyme@MOF composites significantly increase enzyme stability, protect enzymes from heat/solvents, and improve CO₂ conversion efficiency. As I also showed, MOFs offer high surface area, tunable pores, and a favorable microenvironment for enzymes, critical for biocatalytic CO₂ conversion. However, all published work on enzyme entrapment in MOFs are currently lab- or pilot-scale.</p>

7.	<p>I'm quite new to CCUS:)) and was wondering if by using controlled electron transfer to enzymes, will it also improve the limited mass transfer problem with enzyme immobilisation?</p> <p>Roman: It is one of the motivations of the project. Wiring is beneficial.</p>
8.	<p>Jialong, you mentioned bifunctional reactive dye? Which other dyes are you using?</p> <p>Jialong: We have tried many types of bifunctional dyes and the particular one presented here is Reactive Red 198. Our manuscript that tells more about how we use this dye as a crosslinker was recently published in <i>Carbon Capture Science & Technology</i>: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccst.2026.100599</p>
9.	<p>Can you explain more about why you believe textiles would make good contactors? How do they compare to other materials?</p> <p>Jialong: Textiles are lightweight, economical, flexible, and durable materials that can be fabricated in many shapes and have high surface areas and abundance of functional groups for chemical modification and excellent water transport property for enhanced gas liquid contacts. Compared to other advanced materials, textiles can be easily scaled up owing to its global manufacturing infrastructure that is able to produce large volumes of materials.</p>
10.	<p>How are the enzymes comparable to existing MEA processes?</p> <p>Joe: Enzymes are much better compared to traditional processes in terms of kinetics (speed up the process), but the process of producing certain enzymes is a bottleneck that needs to be addressed.</p>
11.	<p>Dr. Brunecky, what is the potential for oxygen tolerant FDH enzymes?</p> <p>Roman: <i>E. coli</i> FDH is not oxygen tolerant, which is why we are now investigating MeFDH.</p>
12.	<p>Dr. Brunecky, for simulations that you plan to run on MeFDH-SAM-Gold simulation systems, how is the FDH orientation accounted for? Are NRL teams looking for a specific orientation? Such as minimizing the distance of the iron-sulfur clusters to surface for redox?</p> <p>Roman: Yes we are looking at different orientations.</p>
13.	<p>Does the location and placement of immobilized enzymes affect their activity?</p> <p>Jialong: Yes, immobilized enzymes placed close to the gas-liquid interface exhibit higher apparent activity. For this reason, careful design of the immobilization strategies are needed to take full advantage of the enzyme catalysis.</p>

Session 2: Advancing

14.	<p>We heard that making FDH is challenging - do you see this as a roadblock?</p> <p>Yong Hwan: Yes - due to the W-bis-MGD, which is oxygen sensitive. You can learn more about MeFDH1 structure and the W-bis-MGD ligand in our <i>Scientific Reports</i></p>
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	publication: https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-54205-7
15.	<p>What is your opinion on “free” versus immobilized enzymes? Do you see one as better than the other?</p> <p>Sara: It will depend on what the application is. Several things will matter: Mass diffusion, immobilization chemistry, steric hindrance.</p>
16.	<p>How do enzyme-based technologies compare to other technologies you are working with?</p> <p>Lasse: Enzyme-based – or enzyme-enhanced – technologies compare well with other pathways. Typically, the enzymes are used to reduce energy costs of capture in amine-based systems, or accelerate kinetics in conversion processes that would otherwise be very slow. In amine-based systems, enzymes can reduce energy consumption by several 10's of %. Other processes are more exploratory and it is too early to quantify their potential, but the potential to be competitive is definitely there. At CORC, our ambition is to develop processes that reach around 1 GJ/tCO₂, with current industrial processes at around 3-4 GJ/tCO₂.</p>
17.	<p>Based on research data generated thus far, what is the economic feasibility of CO₂ to protein? How does it compete with incumbent protein sources, namely meat?</p> <p>Sara: Can be a drug synthesis approach. Not on the stage of assessing TEA yet.</p> <p>Lasse: Converting CO₂ to protein requires much less land usage. Conventional method costs twice as much (estimate)</p>
18.	<p>Does the Novo Nordisk sponsored CORC have any plan to extend in non enzymatic ways of CO₂ conversion, such as thermochemicals and if the organization is open to collaborate on those non-enzymatic ways of CO₂ conversion.</p> <p>Lasse: CORC is very open to collaborate on CO₂ conversions using either way.</p>
19.	<p>Professor Kim, what is needed to scale up your FDH-based technology?</p> <p>Yong Hwan: While various strategies to move from lab scale to larger testing scales are still in development, you can read about our recent scale-up efforts using a combined ChCODH2 and MeFDH1 enzymatic approach for molar-scale formate production from industrial off-gas in our <i>Nature Chemical Engineering</i> article: https://doi.org/10.1038/s44286-024-00063-z</p>
20.	<p>I was curious to know, what immobilization strategy do you recommend for MeFDH1 to keep good activity and stability during continuous CO₂ conversion?</p> <p>Yong Hwan: The enzyme needs to be properly oriented - to transfer electrons well. I have used Ni-NTA as an immobilized bead, as reported in our <i>Nature Chemical Engineering</i> article: https://doi.org/10.1038/s44286-024-00063-z However, it is not yet oriented to immobilize the enzyme to facilitate electron transfer, and more research is needed.</p>
21.	<p>What is the best way for researchers to collaborate with BIG?</p> <p>Sonja: First, participating in events like this with us is a great way to collaborate - sharing knowledge can spark ideas for how to overcome a problem or embark on a new research direction. Also, please reach out directly to any team member if you have a specific idea to discuss, such as inviting a member of the team as a guest speaker,</p>

	discussing a research method, or collaborating on a funding proposal.
22.	<p>Sonja, you said you've been working on enzymatic carbon capture for a long time, but you're still at research scale - what is needed to move the technology forward?</p> <p>Sonja: Finding pilot-scale and field test projects in scenarios that especially benefit from what carbonic anhydrase can offer that other systems can't is a critical next step. In the introduction, I emphasized that immobilized CA can speed up absorber-only processes. This approach eliminates the costly desorption step, but you have to use "solvents" that are different from conventional capture processes. For example, solvents, like alkaline brines that would not be used in a traditional system, when used with CA can accelerate <i>ex situ</i> CO₂ mineralization for verifiable, durable CO₂ removal.</p>
23.	<p>What could be direct modes of collaboration between researchers associated with BIG and CORC?</p> <p>Sonja & Lasse: We already have examples of collaboration through joint membership by DTU on both teams, and BIG has hosted guest speakers from CORC. We encourage members from both teams to identify possibilities for exchange visits between labs and we will look into the possibility of hosting a joint event, either virtual or in-person, that promotes knowledge-sharing and future research planning.</p>

Section 4: Participation Summary

Table 4.1. Registered vs Attendance

Total registered for the event	94
Total unregistered at the event using open link access	5
Total in attendance at the event	69

Table 4.2. Day of Event Attendance

Unique Total Participants who joined at least one session	69
Total Speakers + Moderators + Support Staff	14
Total Participants from BIG Team	23
Total External Participants (including external speakers)	46
Number of Countries Represented	10

Section 5: Research Links

- [Biocatalyst Interactions with Gases \(BIG\) Collaboration](#)
- [BIG Collaboration TTVE Website](#)
- [BIG Zenodo Community Site](#)
- [National Lab of the Rockies \(NLR\)](#)
- [Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology \(UNIST\)](#)
- [Novonosis](#)

- [Novo Nordisk Foundation CO2 Research Center \(CORC\)](#)
- [2025 BIG Research Symposium](#)

Thanks for your interest in this work - stay involved!

Summary prepared by Angie Shows and Sonja Salmon with input from event participants.
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